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ABSTRACT

Hybrid bionanocomposites with shape memory behavior are reported. The materials were accessed by combining a polyurethane matrix with a high renewable carbon content, cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs), and magnetite nanoparticles (MNPs). The integration of the two nanoparticle types resulted in tough materials that display a higher stiffness and storage modulus in the glassy and rubbery state, thus contributing to the structural reinforcement, as well as magnetic properties, reflecting a synergistic effect of this combination. A quantitative characterization of the thermo-activated shape-memory effect made evident that the addition of CNCs increases the shape fixity, due to the higher glass transition temperature (T_g) and the higher stiffness below T_g than the neat PU, while the addition of MNPs made it possible to activate the shape recovery by applying an alternating magnetic field. Moreover, the new hybrid bionanocomposites showed good bio- and hemo-compatibility.

Keywords:

Hybrid polyurethane bionanocomposites, magnetite nanoparticles, cellulose nanocrystals, thermo- and magneto-response, biocompatibility.

IMPACT OF THE COMBINED USE OF MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES AND CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS ON THE SHAPE-MEMORY BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID POLYURETHANE BIONANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid bionanocomposites with shape memory behavior are reported. The materials were accessed by combining a polyurethane matrix with a high renewable carbon content, cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs), and magnetite nanoparticles (MNPs). The integration of the two nanoparticle types resulted in tough materials that display a higher stiffness and storage modulus in the glassy and rubbery state, thus contributing to the structural reinforcement, as well as magnetic properties, reflecting a synergistic effect of this combination. A quantitative characterization of the thermo-activated shape-memory effect made evident that the addition of CNCs increases the shape fixity, due to the higher glass transition temperature (T_g) and the higher stiffness below T_g than the neat PU, while the addition of MNPs made it possible to activate the shape recovery by applying an alternating magnetic field. Moreover, the new hybrid bionanocomposites showed good bio- and hemo-compatibility.

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INTRODUCTION

The interest in the design of new advanced polymeric nanocomposites has increased in the last decades, since the incorporation of nanoparticles into polymeric matrices can improve the mechanical properties and provide new functionalities to the resulting materials.^{1,2} In general, nanocomposites are prepared by the incorporation of a nanofiller into a polymer matrix and, depending on the nature of the nanofiller, this leads to an improvement of the mechanical properties,^{3,4} thermal stability,⁵ or the thermo-mechanical stability.⁶ Nanoparticles can also bestow the material with specific functions, such as electrically conducting,⁷ magnetic,^{8,9} antioxidant,¹⁰ or antimicrobial¹¹ behavior, among others. Nanocomposites made with two or more nanoparticles have emerged as a particularly intriguing platform, as such materials often not only combine the properties imparted by the different components, but also a synergic effect between the nanofillers can take place, providing the matrix with new and in some cases emergent properties.¹ Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) have gained particular interest due to their low specific mass, high stiffness, and high strength, which result in excellent specific mechanical properties, which are even higher than the one of metals.¹² Moreover, cellulose is also outstanding according to its availability, inherent renewability, low cost, biocompatibility and biodegradability.¹³⁻¹⁵ On the other hand, magnetic nanoparticles, such as magnetite, can provide magnetic properties to the matrix and they can be used to absorb and convert the energy of an alternating magnetic field (AMF) into heat.^{8,16} While several studies have focused on combining CNCs and magnetic nanoparticles, for example by modifying cellulose with magnetite¹⁷ to produce conductive paper and with maghemite¹⁸ to create materials for toxic metal removal, to our best knowledge, there have been no reports on polymer nanocomposites made by combining CNCs and magnetite nanoparticles (MNPs) in a polymeric matrix.

We here report that the combined integration of CNCs and MNPs into a shape-memory polymer (SMP) affords materials with properties that are not accessible by using either of the nanofillers alone. SMPs are macromolecular materials that can be used to produce objects that can be remodeled into a temporary shape and eventually recover their original (permanent) shape. Both the remodeling and the recovery processes require applying an external stimulus, for instance heat, electric or magnetic fields, light, pH, or moisture.^{19,20} Thermo-responsive materials in which the shape remodeling and recovery are enabled by direct heating are the most reported SMPs. These polymers are typically composed of two different phases, a physically or chemically cross-linked deformable network that controls the memorization of the permanent shape, and a stimuli-responsive phase that acts as a switch and allows the fixation of the temporary shape. In thermo-

responsive SMPs, the switchable phase exhibits a phase transition that is characterized by a transition temperature (T_{trans}), normally a melting (T_m) or a glass transition temperature (T_g).²¹ Shape remodeling is achieved by heating the object to a switching temperature (T_s), above T_{trans} , deforming the object at this temperature by applying mechanical forces, and cooling the deformed object to a temperature below T_{trans} . This temporary shape is stable as long as the temperature remains below T_{trans} , but the originally shaped object is recoverable by heating above T_{trans} .²² Segmented thermoplastic polyurethanes (STPUs) represent the perhaps most widely investigated family of SMPs.^{1,23–26} These polymers are composed of two different segments, a telechelic macrodiol-based soft segment and a hard segment obtained by reacting a diisocyanate with a diol-chain extender, usually a low-molecular-weight diol. The two segments are generally immiscible so that microphase separation takes place, but this process depends greatly on the length and the chemical composition of the segments.^{27,28} Therefore, the properties of STPUs can easily be tuned by modifying their chemical structure via the choice of the various building blocks. In this context, biomass-derived monomers, such as produced from vegetable oil, polysaccharides, or aminoacids, are receiving growing attention, as their sourcing is often environmentally more friendly than that of petrochemical-based counterparts.^{29–31} For example, we previously reported³² an STPU based on the bio-based asymmetric ethyl ester L-lysine diisocyanate (LDI), the corn-sugar-sourced chain extender 1,3-propanediol (PD) and a bio-based crystallizable macrodiol. Interestingly, the T_g of the amorphous hard phase formed by the reaction of LDI and PD was below the melting temperature of the macrodiol phase, and this “inverted” the functions of the two phases: while in typical segmented thermoplastic polyurethane shape-memory polymers (STPU-SMPs) the macrodiol domains represent the switchable phase while the hard-segments form the physical network that provides the permanent shape, the phases in the previously reported bio-based STPU-SMPs have the opposite functions, i.e., the macrodiol domains maintain the network and the LDI-PD segments serve as switching element.

One of the major drawbacks of SMPs is that they show smaller stresses/forces than shape-memory ceramics and alloys, on account of their lower stiffness.³³ One of the ways to overcome this disadvantage is to mechanically reinforce SMPs with CNCs^{16,34–36} or another reinforcing filler.^{37–40} To address the issue that in certain applications the direct heating of the shape-memory object is not possible, magnetic nanoparticles such as magnetite, have been incorporated, which, as aforementioned, can be heated by an externally applied alternating magnetic field.^{41,42}

The main goal of this study was to access new hybrid bionanocomposites with advanced properties by combining a bio-based STPU-SMP with MNPs and CNCs. To that end, the effect of the combination of these two nanoparticle types on the final properties was explored. The physico-chemical, thermal, and mechanical characteristics of the materials were characterized by means of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), X-ray diffraction (XRD), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and tensile testing, while their shape-memory function was elucidated by means of heat-controlled cyclic shape-memory experiments. In addition, the possibility to remotely trigger the shape recovery in response to an alternating magnetic field was explored. The *in-vitro* biocompatibility of the new hybrid composites was probed by cell-viability assays, hemocompatibility experiments, and cell-adhesion studies.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The bio-based STPU-SMP matrix was synthesized by a catalyst-free, two-step polymerization protocol as previously reported.³² Ethyl ester L-lysine diisocyanate (LDI) (bio-based carbon content (BBC) of 81% determined by ASTM-D6886 standard procedure) (CHEMOS GmbH), 1,3-propanediol (PD) made from corn sugar (BCC of 100%) (Quimidroga S.A.), and a castor oil based macrodiol, poly(butylene sebacate)diol (hydroxyl index of 32.01 mg KOH g⁻¹, number-average molecular weight of 3500 g mol⁻¹⁴³, BCC of 72%) were used as monomers. The molar ratio of the monomers was 1:5.05:4 (macrodiol:LDI:PD), affording a PU with a BCC of 75% and a LDI/PD fraction of 29 wt%. The average mass and number molecular weight and polydispersity index were 100,000 g mol⁻¹, 40,000 g mol⁻¹ and 2.5, respectively.³² The chemical structure of the STPU-SMP was confirmed in a previous study.¹⁶ A polyurethane made by the reaction of LDI and PD, without the macrodiol, was also synthesized for reference purposes (LDI/PD). The MNPs employed here had a diameter of 8.0 ± 2.2 nm (determined by transmission electron microscopy), were stabilized with chemisorbed and physisorbed oleic acid, and prepared via a co-precipitation method as reported previously.¹⁶ The MNPs were stored dispersed in THF at a concentration of 4 g L⁻¹ in a refrigerator at 4 °C. The CNCs were isolated from microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) having a particle size between 100 and 150 μm (Aldrich) by acid hydrolysis with sulfuric acid (96%, Panreac) following a previously reported protocol.⁴⁴ The isolated CNCs were of rod-like shape with an average diameter $D = 7 \pm 2$ nm and an average length $L = 146 \pm 16$ nm (both determined by AFM from phase image and height profile, respectively), resulting in an aspect ratio of $L/D = 21 \pm 6$. The crystallinity index of the CNCs was 85%, as determined by XRD (for more

details see the supplementary information (Figure S1)). The nanoparticles were dispersed in HPLC grade tetrahydrofuran (THF, Macron Fine Chemicals). THF was also used to prepare the bionanocomposites.

L929 murine fibroblast cells (from ATCC) were employed for biocompatibility studies. Minimum Essential Medium to which 1 mM sodium Pyruvate, 10% FBS (fetal bovine serum, Biochrom AG, Berlin, Germany), 1nM penicillin-streptomycin (Lonza, Verviers, Belgium), and 1% non-essential amino acids (Gibco, Paisley, UK) were added was used to culture the cells.

Materials processing

A solvent casting method was employed to prepare hybrid bionanocomposite films. First, 7.5 and 12.5 mL of the MNP dispersion (4 g L^{-1} in THF) were combined with 17.5 and 17 mL of a 50 mg mL^{-1} solution of the bio-based polyurethane in THF in order to create composites with a final weight fraction of 3 and 5% of MNPs. The mixtures were placed into a sonication bath and sonicated for 1 h. Concurrently, a suspension of 5 mg mL^{-1} of CNCs in THF was sonicated for 4 h in a sonication bath that was cooled with a cold-water recirculation system, to prepare composites with a fixed CNC weight fraction of 10 wt% with respect to the total mass (1 g). The two polymer/MNP mixtures were each combined with 20 mL of the CNC dispersion and the mixtures were sonicated for 30 min and then casted into poly(tetrafluoroethylene) molds. The solvent was removed by placing the molds for 20 h in an oven kept at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the remaining solids were compression-molded into 0.2 mm thick films at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a pressure of 5 bar, and a time of 5 min in the press. For reference purposes, films of the neat polyurethane and a bionanocomposite containing only 10 wt% of the CNCs were also prepared. Pictures of the films thus obtained are shown in Figure 1. Samples are coded PU-xMNP-CNC, with x expressing the weight fraction (wt%) of the MNPs. The reference materials containing only the polymer or the polymer and the CNCs are referred to as PU and PU-CNC, respectively.

Figure 1. Digital image of the neat PU and the PU-based hybrid bionanocomposite films containing 10 wt% CNCs and 0, 3, or 5 wt% MNPs (size: $5 \times 5 \text{ cm}^2$).

Characterization

The crystallinity of the CNCs and the bionanocomposites was established from X-ray diffraction (XRD) data. To that end, a Philips X'pert PRO automatic diffractometer operating in theta-theta configuration with an operating voltage of 40 kV and a current of 40 mA was used. A secondary monochromator with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) was employed and diffracted X-rays were monitored using a PIXcel solid state detector (active length in $2\theta = 3.347^\circ$). A fixed divergence / antiscattering slit was used to keep the irradiated sample volume constant.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were taken on a Nanoscope IIIa (Multimode™ Digital Instruments) scanning probe microscope in tapping mode. An integrated force generated by cantilever/silicon probes was employed. The resonance frequency was 180 kHz, the length of the cantilever was 125 μm , and the radius of the tip 5-10 nm. To image the CNCs, they were dispersed in THF (0.1 wt%) by sonicating for 1 h. The CNCs were deposited on a mica substrate by placing a drop of the dispersion on the substrate and spin coating at 1200 rpm for 120 s.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were made using a Mettler Toledo DSC3+ equipped with an intracooler and with N₂ (20 mL min⁻¹) as purge gas. Experiments were carried out with samples weighing 5-10 mg in sealed aluminum pans, heating from -75 to 100 °C at a rate of 20 °C min⁻¹, and subsequent cooling from 100 to -75 °C at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The T_g was determined from the inflection point of the observed heat capacity change in the first heating trace, while T_m represents the maximum of the endothermic peak observed during the first heating. The area under this peak afforded the melting enthalpy (ΔH_m). Furthermore, the crystallization temperature (T_c) was established from the exothermic peak's maximum in the first cooling trace, while the area under this peak afforded the crystallization enthalpy (ΔH_c). The ΔH_m and ΔH_c values were normalized against the total sample weight.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was employed to study the thermo-mechanical characteristics of the hybrid bionanocomposites and the reference materials. To that end, an Eplexor 100N analyzer (Gabo) operated in tensile mode and with an applied static strain of 0.10% was used. A heating scan from -100 to 75 °C (2 °C min⁻¹) was performed and the operation frequency was fixed at 10 Hz. Strip-shaped samples were cut with dimensions of 22 mm x 5 mm x 0.2 mm (length x width x thickness).

A Universal Testing Machine equipped with pneumatic grips and a load cell of 250 N (MTS Insight 10) was used to carry out uniaxial tensile tests. Samples were stretched at

room temperature until failure and at 40 °C to a strain of 200%, using a controlled temperature chamber (Thermcraft). Samples were cut into strips with the same dimensions as the ones employed for DMA. Tests were performed with a least five specimen applying a crosshead rate of 50 mm min⁻¹.

The shape-memory properties of the new hybrid nanocomposites and the reference materials were also measured on the Universal Testing Machine and temperature chamber in strain-controlled mode. Strip-shaped samples similar to the ones used for DMA and tensile tests were heated for 10 min at T_s = 40 °C. After that, the samples were stretched at strain = 50% at a strain rate of 5 mm min⁻¹ and subsequently cooled down to ca. -10 °C without removing the stress to fix the temporary shape, using a cooling spray (Freezer 5320, Jelt) for 1 min. Once the sample was cold, the applied stress was released. Finally, samples were heated at T_s for 10 min to restore the original shape. Five consecutive fix/release cycles were carried out. In order to quantify the thermally activated shape-memory response shape fixity (R_f) and shape recovery (R_r) values were taken into account, which are calculated using equation 1 and 2, respectively.

$$R_f(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_u(N)}{\varepsilon_m(N)} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$R_r(N) = \frac{\varepsilon_m(N) - \varepsilon_p(N)}{\varepsilon_m(N) - \varepsilon_p(N-1)} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

where ε_m is the maximum strain applied during programming, ε_u reflects the resulting residual strain that was determined after the cooling and unloading, ε_p represents the residual strain measured after the shape had been recovered, and N indicates the cycle number.

A Magnetherm V1.5 device from Nanotherics Ltd. was used to test the magneto-responsive shape-memory recovery. The device featured a nine-turn solenoid, which worked at 15.9 kA m⁻¹ and 523.5 kHz. Moreover, a Power Cube 32/1800 HF2 device, working with a 1018 kHz high-frequency generator was employed in order to trigger the magnetically induced shape-recovery effect. The setup had a coil with a diameter of 4 mm, and produced a magnetic flux density of 21 mT.

In vitro cytotoxicity, cell adhesion, and hemocompatibility assays of the new hybrid bionanocomposites were carried out following the ISO 10993 (2009) standard.⁴⁵ For cytotoxicity tests, the materials were incubated in the complete media to obtain the extractive media, while for hemocompatibility tests, incubation was done in phosphate buffered saline (PBS). In both cases, the samples were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C.

PrestoBlue® (Invitrogen, USA) was employed to assess the cytotoxicity of the hybrid bionanocomposites. This resazurin-based solution acts as a colorimetric indicator for cell viability. Assays were carried out following the protocol described in ISO 10993- 5 and 12:2009^{45,46} standards. Briefly, L929 cells (murine fibroblasts) were placed at a density of 4×10^3 cells/well in 100 μ L of complete culture medium into 96-well plates. The medium was replaced by 100 μ L of the extractive media of the biomaterial, high-density polyethylene in complete medium (considered as the negative control) or polyvinyl chloride in dimethyl sulfoxide and a 10% of the complete medium (positive control) after 24 h. A synergy HC spectrophotometer (Biotek, USA) was used to measure the optical density (OD) at 570 nm at different times (0, 24, 48 and 72h). All the assays were performed three times. The viability of the prepared materials' cells was determined from equation 3:

$$\text{Viability (\%)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{negative control}}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

where sample cells' absorbance is $\text{OD}_{\text{sample}}$ and the one of the negative control cells is $\text{OD}_{\text{negative control}}$.

Cyanomethemoglobin was used for hemocompatibility tests following the protocol recommended by ISO 10993-4:2009.⁴⁷ According to this method, during hemolysis red cells release hemoglobin, which in presence of ferricyanide and bicarbonate can be turn into cyanomethemoglobin, whose absorbance can be measured at 540nm.⁴⁸ The blood of three healthy C57BL/6 mice was treated with Li-heparin to prevent coagulation. The assay was performed using a pool of the blood samples with a concentration lower than 1 mg mL⁻¹ of free hemoglobin plasma. To that end, the concentration of the total blood hemoglobin (TBHd) was adjusted to 10 mg mL⁻¹ by diluting pooled blood with 1 x PBS. Subsequently aliquots of TBHd (100 μ L) and 1 x PBS (700 μ L) were mixed with sample extracted media (100 μ L), positive (1% Tritron X-100) or negative (polyethylene glycol solution at 40%) controls for the evaluation of bionanocomposites' potential hemolytic effect. Samples were then placed into an incubator and kept at 37 °C for 3 h before they were centrifuged at 800 g for 15 min. The hemoglobin concentration in the supernatant of the samples was then calculated using a cyanomethemoglobin standard curve at an absorbance of 540 nm according to equation 4:

$$\text{Hemolysis (\%)} = \frac{\text{sample hemoglobin concentration} - \text{negative control concentration}}{\text{positive control concentration} - \text{negative control concentration}} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

A Hitachi S-4800 scanning electron microscope was used to study the morphology and the adhesion of the L929 cells on the surface of the hybrid bionanocomposites. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were acquired with an accelerating voltage of 15 kV at times of 24, 48 and 72 h. The samples were placed in 24-well ultra-low attachment plates before the cells were seeded (cells density: 1×10^5 cells cm^{-2}). After that, at each time point at which SEM images were acquired, the samples were washed three times with Sorensen buffer (Panreac AppliChem, Spain), fixed with 2% glutaraldehyde (Panreac) in 0.1 M cacodylate buffer, stained with 1% OsO_4 for 1 h, and finally rinsed with PBS. A series of aqueous ethanol solutions of different concentration was used to dehydrate the samples and hexamethyldisilazane was employed to dry them for 10 min. Finally, a thin layer of gold was sputtered, under argon, onto the samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bio-based STPU-SMP matrix employed here was synthesized by a catalyst-free, two-step polymerization protocol as previously reported,³² the MNPs employed were synthesized via an established co-precipitation method,¹⁶ and CNCs were obtained by acidic hydrolysis of microcrystalline cellulose using a known route.⁴⁴ Films of the bio-based shape-memory polyurethane (PU) as reference, and the (hybrid) bionanocomposites containing only 10 wt% CNCs (PU-CNC), or 10 wt% CNCs and 3 or 5 wt% MNPs (PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC) were made by solvent casting and reprocessing the solids thus obtained by compression molding. This process afforded films with a thickness of 0.2 mm that were translucent and colorless (PU and PU-CNC) or brown (PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC) (Figure 1).

The thermal behavior of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference films and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposite films was investigated by DSC experiments. We were particularly interested if and how the addition of the two nanofillers would affect the thermal behavior of the PU matrix, notably the transition of the polyol domains exploited for shape memory switching. In Figure 2 the first heating scans of the bionanocomposites with both CNCs and MNPs, with only CNCs, and of the neat biopolyurethane are shown. For reference purposes, we also included the DSC traces of the main constituents of the polyurethane domains, i.e., the poly(butylene sebacate) diol (macrodiol) and the polyurethane formed by LDI/PD. The inset in Figure 2 shows the corresponding cooling traces and Table 1 provides a summary of the thermal transition temperatures extracted from these measurements.

Figure 2. DSC heating scans (first heating) of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites. Also shown are the first heating scans of the macrodiol and of the reference LDI/PD PU. The insets show: the corresponding cooling scans (left), and the heating scans (right) at crystallization and melting intervals, respectively.

Table 1. Thermal transition temperatures and melting and crystallization enthalpies of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites.

Sample	$T_{g\text{LDI/PD}}$ (°C)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J g ⁻¹)	T_c (°C)	ΔH_c (J g ⁻¹)
PU	13.6	64.6	62.8	41.9	-58.8
PU-CNC	14.1	60.3	58.2	40.5	-54.2
PU-3MNP-CNC	14.5	60.3	51.3	42.0	-49.8
PU-5MNP-CNC	14.5	59.3	52.4	41.8	-49.0

Several transitions ascribed to the different domains formed by the macrodiol and LDI/PD are observable in the DSC traces of the various materials, reflecting microphase separated microstructures. The DSC trace of the semicrystalline macrodiol shows an endothermic signal with a peak centered at 70 °C, which indicates the melting of the crystalline fraction. The thermogram of the amorphous LDI/PD shows a T_g at 33 °C. The DSC trace of the neat biopolyurethane shows a T_g at 13.6 °C, which must be associated with the LDI/PD-rich domain ($T_{g\text{LDI/PD}}$) and a T_m at 64.6 °C that is linked to the macrodiol rich-domain. Note again that in contrast to most PU-SMPs, where the hard segments

define the permanent shape and a phase change of the phase formed by the macrodiol is used as the switch, the functions are inverted in the present PU, because the T_g of the LDI/PD rich phase is lower than the T_m of the macrodiol. All of the bionanocomposites also show a T_g related to the domains formed by LDI/PD in the same temperature interval and a broad endothermic signal ascribed to melting of the domains constituted by the crystalline macrodiol (inset of the right). The T_m is slightly reduced to 59-60°C, suggesting that the crystallization process is slightly impacted by the nanoparticles.⁴⁹ In addition, the overall crystallinity of the bionanocomposites with CNCs and both nanofillers decreases, as reflected by the lower ΔH_m . This decrease is more noticeable when both nanoentities are combined, but no dependence of the MNP content can be seen. In the DSC cooling traces a corresponding behavior is seen (left inset in Figure 2), i.e., a decrease of T_c and ΔH_c can be observed. The observed variations of the crystallinity upon addition of the different nanoentities are also corroborated by XRD (see supplementary information (Figure S2)) experiments, which show that the intensity of the peak at 21.4° is lower in the case of the bionanocomposites than in the neat PU, especially for the hybrid bionanocomposites.

The analysis of the dynamic mechanical behavior across different temperatures is important to rationally exploit the shape-memory function of the polymers, since the changes of the storage modulus (E') and thermal transitions directly impact the thermo-responsive shape-memory behavior.⁵⁰⁻⁵² Therefore, the mechanical characteristics of the various materials were analyzed as a function of temperature. The E' and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) of the PU reference and bionanocomposites are shown as a function of temperature in Figure 3. At low temperature (data are quoted for -75 °C), where the amorphous fraction is in a glassy state, the bionanocomposites show a higher E' (PU-CNC = 2560 MPa, PU-3MNP-CNC = 2666 MPa, and PU-5MNP-CNC = 3085 MPa) than the neat PU (2360 MPa). At higher temperatures, a step-wise decrease of the E' is observed, with a first maximum of the $\tan \delta$ around 19-24 °C that is related to the glass transition of the LDI/PD-rich domains. As is evident from the $\tan \delta$ curves, the maximum temperature increases with the addition of the nanofillers (PU = 19 °C, PU-CNC = 23 °C, PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC = 24 °C). A second modulus reduction step appears to set in around 50°C, and all samples fail around 60 °C, where the semicrystalline macrodiol-rich domains melt. Thus, the materials under investigation feature a narrow rubbery plateau in the range of ca. 30-50°C where shape programming and release is possible. Across the entire temperature range, the E' of the bionanocomposites is higher than that of the neat PU matrix, and E' increases with the

nanofiller content, suggesting that both CNCs and MNPs contribute to the structural reinforcement.

Figure 3. Storage modulus E' and $\tan \delta$ vs temperature of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites as a function of temperature. The inset shows the storage modulus in the magnified low-temperature region.

Since the maximum strain that can be applied in the programming step of the thermo-mechanical cyclic test relevant for the shape-memory effect, the mechanical characteristics of the neat PU and PU-CNC references and of the hybrid bionanocomposites were further studied by tensile testing. In Figure 3 the stress-strain curves measured at 25 °C are shown and in Table 2 the Young modulus (E), yield stress (σ_y), yield strain (ϵ_y), stress at break (σ_b) and strain at break (ϵ_b) values are summarized. As can be observed, the incorporation of CNCs results in materials with higher stiffness, yield stress, and stress at break, whereas the strain at break decreases slightly. This behavior is in good agreement with the data reported for other CNC-reinforced polyurethanes.^{53–55} As already reflected by the DMA experiments, the bionanocomposites containing both nanofillers display a similar or even higher E than the bionanocomposite containing only CNCs. Regarding σ_y and σ_b , the bionanocomposites show similar values as the neat matrix, while in general lower ϵ_b values were observed. However, it is noteworthy that PU-3MNP-CNC shows the highest ϵ_b value, similar to the neat matrix. This fact might be attributable the formation of a percolating CNC network⁵⁶ and additional reinforcement by the MNPs.^{16,57} Thus, the combination of CNCs with MNPs, leads to a tough magnetic bionanocomposite with a high elastic modulus without a significant compromise in the strain at break.

Since the shape-memory programming requires deformation above the T_g , tensile tests were also performed at 40 °C. The inset of Figure 4 shows that all stress-strain curves thus recorded are very similar to the one's measured at 25 °C. Moreover, as shown in Table 2, the bionanocomposites show a higher yield stress and E than the neat PU. The difference of the mechanical behavior at the two temperatures resides in the lower stress at yield and E values observed at 40 °C, due to the higher chain mobility at temperatures above the T_g .

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites. The inset shows a magnification of the stress-strain curves measured at 25 and 40 °C.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites.^a

Sample	E (25°C) (MPa)	E (40°C) (MPa)	σ_y (25°C) (MPa)	σ_y (40°C) (MPa)	σ_b (25°C) (MPa)	ϵ_y (25°C) (%)	ϵ_y (40°C) (%)	ϵ_b (25°C) (%)
PU	92.9 ± 7.6	63.8 ± 9.5	6.9 ± 0.2	5.1 ± 1.3	7.2 ± 0.4	16.9 ± 2.2	12.7 ± 3.3	1149 ± 153
PU-CNC	106.8 ± 2.9	68.6 ± 9.0	7.4 ± 0.2	5.3 ± 1.0	7.4 ± 0.1	14.7 ± 0.3	13.9 ± 5.0	857 ± 11
PU-3MNP-CNC	106.4 ± 3.4	86.7 ± 8.1	7.8 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 1.1	7.5 ± 0.1	14.3 ± 2.3	11.1 ± 2.1	1160 ± 83
PU-5MNP-CNC	165.8 ± 9.1	102.3 ± 7.1	7.8 ± 0.3	5.6 ± 0.9	6.7 ± 0.5	11.7 ± 2.2	11.3 ± 1.6	779 ± 14

^aYoung modulus (E), yield stress (σ_y), stress at break (σ_b), yield strain (ϵ_y), and strain at break (ϵ_b) measured at 25 and 40 °C.

Figure 5. Stress-strain curves acquired in five subsequent programming-release cycles of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites.

Table 3. R_f and R_r values of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites ($T_s = 40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min, $\varepsilon_m = 50\%$). Data for five subsequent programming-release cycles are shown.

Cycle	PU		PU-CNC		PU-3MNP-CNC		PU-5MNP-CNC	
	R_f (%)	R_r (%)	R_f (%)	R_r (%)	R_f (%)	R_r (%)	R_f (%)	R_r (%)
1	91.6	87.3	96.5	86.2	98.3	86.1	97.0	85.5
2	93.4	99.3	98.7	96.7	98.5	93.8	99.1	97.5
3	94.8	99.5	98.7	97.7	98.8	97.9	99.1	98.7
4	96.4	99.5	98.7	99.4	98.8	99.6	99.2	98.9
5	99.4	100.0	98.9	100.0	99.1	99.1	99.6	100.0

Next, the shape-memory behavior of the neat PU and the PU-CNC reference materials, and the PU-3MNP-CNC and PU-5MNP-CNC hybrid bionanocomposites was determined using a tensile tester in strain-controlled mode (see Experimental Section for details). To program a temporary shape, samples were heated and maintained at $T_s = 40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min, this temperature was chosen based on a previous study,³² before they were stretched to a strain of 50%, and then cooled, without removing the stress, to a temperature of around $-10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, previous to the release of the stress. Finally, samples were heated back to T_s and kept at this temperature for 10 min to restore the original shape. This cycle of programming and releasing a temporary shape was repeated for each sample five times. The corresponding stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 5 and the shape fixity (R_f) and shape recovery (R_r) parameters extracted from these experiments are shown in Table 3. The R_f and R_r values determined in the first programming cycle show that the shape fixity is the parameter that is influenced the most by the incorporation of the nanofillers, since all bionanocomposites show higher R_f values than the neat PU. This increase could be related to the contribution of the nanoparticles to increase the E' in the glassy state, as previously reported by Ratna et al.⁵² Moreover, the bionanocomposites show a higher T_g than the neat PU matrix, as observed by DMA, and therefore in the case of the bionanocomposites, a larger fraction of the rubbery fraction has turned glassy during the shape fixing process, resulting in a higher R_f . According to DSC results, the addition of the CNCs and MNPs results in a decrease of the crystallinity, and thereby an increase of the polymer chain mobility, which in turn reduces their hindrance to adopt the lowest entropy state, thus increasing shape fixation.^{41,58} Furthermore, in a previous study, shape-memory bionanocomposites based on the same biopolyurethane matrix and MNPs were reported.¹⁶ The bionanocomposites containing only 3 or 5 wt% of the MNPs showed R_f values of 94.7 and 93.3%, respectively. These values are lower than the values observed for PU-CNC and the hybrid bionanocomposites, but they exceed the R_f of the neat PU. Thus, the combination of both nanoentities – CNCs and MNPs – affords hybrid shape-memory bionanocomposites that display an enhanced shape fixity, suggesting a synergistic effect between both nanoentities.

Regarding the shape recovery, similar R_r values were observed for the bionanocomposites and the neat PU, which is consistent with the fact that this propensity is governed by the crystalline domains.³² Furthermore, although the overall crystallinity decreases, especially in the bionanocomposites with MNPs, the R_r remains similar, suggesting that MNPs could also contribute to the shape recovery. Because all samples were stretched beyond their yield point (ε_y is around 7-8%), plastic deformation occurs

in the first cycle and hence the original shape could not fully be restored in the first cycle, as can be observed in Figure 5. However, R_r increases considerably for the second cycle and no significant variations were seen in the stress-strain curves acquired in the subsequent cycles. After five cycles almost all samples could completely restore their shape. Thus, it can be ascribed to the history of the sample the variation seen in shape-fixity and recovery values between first cycle and the subsequent cycles. In the first cycle, a redistribution of the molecules of the polymeric matrix chains is happening, which involves the reorganization along the stress direction,^{21,59} as evident from the development of the stress-strain curves, which show a quasi-elastic behavior after plastic deformation occurred in the first cycle.

The magnetic response of the bionanocomposites containing CNCs and MNPs was also analyzed. First of all, the magnetic behavior was verified by attracting these materials with a magnet. It was observed that PU and PU-CNC are not magnetic, whereas both bionanocomposites containing MNP are. As an example, in Figure 6 pictures documenting the magnetic behavior of the PU-5MNP-CNC bionanocomposite and the recovery of a previously fixed shape of this material upon applying an AMF of 1018 kHz are shown. As can be observed, the material is able to almost completely restore its original shape rapidly after 13 s. In a previously work, it was seen that a bionanocomposite using the same matrix with 5 wt% of MNPs was also able to restore its original shape in a presence of an AMF after 14 s.¹⁶ Therefore, it can be concluded that the addition of CNCs lead to bionanocomposites with improved shape fixity, which do not interfere on the magnetically activated shape recovery.

Figure 6. a) Pictures revealing the magnetic nature of the PU-5MNP-CNC bionanocomposite. b) Photographic sequence of the evolution of shape recovery of PU-5MNP-CNC triggered by an AMF.

Finally, since SMPs are potentially useful for biomedical applications, the *in vitro* bio- and hemo- compatibility of the PU-CNC and PU-3MNP-CNC bionanocomposite were

analyzed by means of short-term cytotoxicity, cell adhesion, and hemocompatibility assays. Regarding the cell viability, the response of both bionanocomposites is similar to the behavior of the negative control (Figure 7a), and exceeds the accepted limit of 70%, as outlined by ISO 10993-5 standard.⁴⁶ Thus, the bionanocomposites investigated here show a non-toxic behavior. Furthermore, the integrity of the membranes of red blood cells was analyzed to study the interaction of the materials with blood. According to Figure 7b, while the cells of the positive control are completely lysed, the hemolysis of PU-CNC and PU-3MNP-CNC bionanocomposites is below the accepted limit of 5%, as detailed in ISO 10993-4 standard,⁴⁷ meaning that both materials are hemocompatible. Moreover, a comparison of the hemolysis values of a bionanocomposite with 3 wt% of MNPs (4.6%),¹⁶ PU-CNC (3.8%) and PU-3MNP-CNC (3.6%) shows that bionanocomposites containing both nanoparticles exhibit slightly lower lysis. In addition, as can be seen in Figure 7c the supernatant of the positive control is red, whereas the ones of both bionanocomposites is colorless, denoting that the prepared materials have a negative hemolytic response. Finally, the cell adhesion was also analyzed. In Figure 7d SEM images of cells cultured on the surface of the bionanocomposites can be observed. Cells are well adhered to the surface and, as can be seen in the enlarged image, they acquire a flattened morphology. Moreover, it can be observed that adhesion of the cells is stable due to the presence of multiple cytoplasmic projections. In sight of the preliminary results, the studied bionanocomposites not only are *in vitro* biocompatible, but also hemocompatible.

a)

Figure 7. Evaluation of the biocompatibility of PU-CNC and PU-3MNP-CNC bionanocomposites by *in-vitro* assays. a) Chart showing the outcomes of a cytotoxicity assay of the bionanocomposites and a negative control. The dashed line denotes the acceptance limit of 70%. b) Chart showing the outcome of hemocompatibility (%hemolysis) induced by the material extract. (c) Images showing the hemolytic response of the bionanocomposites and a positive control. (d) SEM Images of L929 cells that had been cultured on the surface of the bionanocomposites after. The images were acquired after 72 h with a magnification of left: 500X, right: 2000X.

CONCLUSIONS

Shape-memory bionanocomposites showing a thermal and magnetic response were obtained and characterized based on a polyurethane matrix with a high renewable carbon content and two nanoparticle types, CNCs and MNPs. The effect that the incorporation of the two nanocomponents had on the composites' properties was studied. The addition of MNPs and CNCs allowed modifying the thermal and thermo-mechanical characteristics by decreasing the crystallinity of the polyol phase in the

polyurethane matrix and increasing the T_g of the domains formed by the LDI/PD urethane segments, and increasing the storage modulus at all temperatures. Furthermore, the analysis of the mechanical properties revealed that tough materials were obtained. Moreover, the combination of CNCs with MNPs afforded magnetic bionanocomposites with high elastic modulus without compromising the strain at break. The incorporation of CNCs contributed an increased shape fixity, while the addition of MNPs provided the bionanocomposites with the capability to restore the original shape by applying an alternating magnetic field. The combination of both nanoentities allowed the rapid and nearly full recovery of the original shape upon magnetic field exposure. Finally, the analysis of the bio- and hemo-compatibility revealed that bionanocomposites with CNCs and both CNCs and MNPs were both bio- and hemo-compatible. Moreover, a synergistic effect was observed for bionanocomposites with CNCs and MNPs, since those properties were enhanced. In this way, the combination of CNCs and MNPs allowed the obtaining of shape-memory bionanocomposites, which can be triggered via an indirect method, with higher shape fixity and suggested that they could be used in the future in the biomedical sector, improving their final properties of the matrix.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

XRD spectrum and AFM images of the isolated cellulose nanocrystals and XRD spectra of the prepared bionanocomposites.

REFERENCES

- (1) Chen, L.; Luque, R.; Li, Y. Controllable Design of Tunable Nanostructures inside Metal-Organic Frameworks. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2017**, *46*, 4614–4630.

- (2) Rescignano, N.; Fortunati, E.; Montesano, S.; Emiliani, C.; Kenny, J. M.; Martino, S.; Armentano, I. PVA Bio-Nanocomposites: A New Take-off Using Cellulose Nanocrystals and PLGA Nanoparticles. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2014**, *99*, 47–58.
- (3) Ifuku, S.; Ikuta, A.; Hosomi, T.; Kanaya, S.; Shervani, Z.; Morimoto, M.; Saimoto, H. Preparation of Polysilsesquioxane-Urethaneacrylate Copolymer Film Reinforced with Chitin Nanofibers. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2012**, *89*, 865–869.
- (4) Paillet, M.; Dufresne, A. Chitin Whisker Reinforced Thermoplastic Nanocomposites. *Macromolecules* **2001**, *34*, 6527–6530.
- (5) Gilman, J. W. Flammability and Thermal Stability Studies of Polymer Layered-Silicate (Clay) Nanocomposites. *Appl. Clay Sci.* **1999**, *15*, 31–49.
- (6) Raza, R.; Ali, S.; Ahmed, F.; Ullah, S.; Grant, J. T.; Iqbal, J. Advance Polymeric Carbon Nanocomposite Films with Enhanced Thermo-Mechanical Properties. *Polym. Compos.* **2011**, *32*, 1757–1765.
- (7) Yao, H.; Wu, L. P.; Chen, G. Q. Synthesis and Characterization of Electroconductive PHA- Graft-Graphene Nanocomposites. *Biomacromolecules* **2019**, *20*, 645–652.
- (8) Zou, H.; Weder, C.; Simon, Y. C. Shape-Memory Polyurethane Nanocomposites with Single Layer or Bilayer Oleic Acid-Coated Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles. *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2015**, *300*, 885–892.
- (9) Yan, X.; He, Q.; Zhang, X.; Gu, H.; Chen, H.; Wang, Q.; Sun, L.; Wei, S.; Guo, Z. Magnetic Polystyrene Nanocomposites Reinforced with Magnetite Nanoparticles. *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2014**, *299*, 485–494.
- (10) Estevez-Areco, S.; Guz, L.; Famá, L.; Candal, R.; Goyanes, S. Bioactive Starch Nanocomposite Films with Antioxidant Activity and Enhanced Mechanical Properties Obtained by Extrusion Followed by Thermo-Compression. *Food Hydrocoll.* **2019**, *96*, 518–528.
- (11) Scaffaro, R.; Botta, L.; Maio, A.; Mistretta, M. C.; La Mantia, F. P. Effect of Graphene Nanoplatelets on the Physical and Antimicrobial Properties of Biopolymer-Based Nanocomposites. *Materials* **2016**, *9*, 351–361.
- (12) Thomas, B.; Raj, M. C.; Athira, B. K.; Rubiyah, H. M.; Joy, J.; Moores, A.; Drisko, G. L.; Sanchez, C. Nanocellulose, a Versatile Green Platform: From Biosources

to Materials and Their Applications. *Chem. Rev.* **2018**, *118*, 11575–11625.

- (13) Kim, H. J.; Park, S.; Kim, S. H.; Kim, J. H.; Yu, H.; Kim, H. J.; Yang, Y. H.; Kan, E.; Kim, Y. H.; Lee, S. H. Biocompatible Cellulose Nanocrystals as Supports to Immobilize Lipase. *J. Mol. Catal. B Enzym.* **2015**, *122*, 170–178.
- (14) Mariano, M.; El Kissi, N.; Dufresne, A. Cellulose Nanocrystals and Related Nanocomposites: Review of Some Properties and Challenges. *J. Polym. Sci. Part B Polym. Phys.* **2014**, *52*, 791–806.
- (15) Endes, C.; Camarero-Espinosa, S.; Mueller, S.; Foster, E. J.; Petri-Fink, A.; Rothen-Rutishauser, B.; Weder, C.; Clift, M. J. D. A Critical Review of the Current Knowledge Regarding the Biological Impact of Nanocellulose. *J. Nanobiotechnology* **2016**, *14*, 78.
- (16) Calvo-Correas, T.; Shirole, A.; Crippa, F.; Fink, A.; Weder, C.; Corcuera, M. A.; Eceiza, A. Biocompatible Thermo- and Magneto-Responsive Shape-Memory Polyurethane Bionanocomposites. *Mater. Sci. Eng. C* **2019**, *97*, 658–668.
- (17) Liu, K.; Nasrallah, J.; Chen, L.; Huang, L.; Ni, Y. Preparation of CNC-Dispersed Fe₃O₄ Nanoparticles and Their Application in Conductive Paper. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2015**, *126*, 175–178.
- (18) Yu, X.; Tong, S.; Ge, M.; Zuo, J.; Cao, C.; Song, W. One-Step Synthesis of Magnetic Composites of Cellulose@iron Oxide Nanoparticles for Arsenic Removal. *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2013**, *1*, 959–965.
- (19) Behl, M.; Lendlein, A. Shape-Memory Polymers. *Mater. Today* **2007**, *10*, 20–28.
- (20) Zhao, Q.; Qi, H. J.; Xie, T. Recent Progress in Shape Memory Polymer: New Behavior, Enabling Materials, and Mechanistic Understanding. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2015**, *49–50*, 79–120.
- (21) Lendlein, A.; Kelch, S. Shape-Memory Polymers. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2002**, *41*, 2034–2057.
- (22) Jeong, H. M.; Song, J. H.; Chi, K. W.; Kim, I.; Kim, K. T. Shape Memory Effect of Poly(Methylene-1,3-Cyclopentane) and Its Copolymer with Polyethylene. *Polym. Int.* **2002**, *51*, 275–280.
- (23) Yang, B.; Huang, W. M.; Li, C.; Li, L. Effects of Moisture on the Thermomechanical Properties of a Polyurethane Shape Memory Polymer. *Polymer* **2006**, *47*, 1348–

1356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2005.12.051>.

- (24) Huang, W. M. Thermo-Moisture Responsive Polyurethane Shape Memory Polymer for Biomedical Devices. *Open Med. Devices J.* **2010**, *2*, 11–19.
- (25) Peponi, L.; Navarro-Baena, I.; Sonseca, A.; Gimenez, E.; Marcos-Fernandez, A.; Kenny, J. M. Synthesis and Characterization of PCL-PLLA Polyurethane with Shape Memory Behavior. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2013**, *49*, 893–903.
- (26) Lin, J. R.; Chen, L. W. Study on Shape-Memory Behavior of Polyether-Based Polyurethanes. I. Influence of the Hard-Segment Content. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **1998**, *69*, 1563–1574.
- (27) Petrovic, Z. S.; Javni, I. Effect of Soft-Segment Length and Concentration on Phase Separation in Segmented Polyurethanes. *J. Polym. Sci. Part B Polym. Phys.* **1989**, *27*, 545–560.
- (28) Wang, C. S.; Kenney, D. J. Effect of Hard Segments on Morphology and Properties of Thermoplastic Polyurethanes. *J. Elastomers Plast.* **1995**, *27*, 182–199.
- (29) Noreen, A.; Zia, K. M.; Zuber, M.; Tabasum, S.; Zahoor, A. F. Bio-Based Polyurethane: An Efficient and Environment Friendly Coating Systems: A Review. *Prog. Org. Coatings* **2016**, *91*, 25–32.
- (30) Charlon, M.; Heinrich, B.; Matter, Y.; Couzigné, E.; Donnio, B.; Avérous, L. Synthesis, Structure and Properties of Fully Biobased Thermoplastic Polyurethanes, Obtained from a Diisocyanate Based on Modified Dimer Fatty Acids, and Different Renewable Diols. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2014**, *61*, 197–205.
- (31) Calvo-Correas, T.; Martin, M. D.; Retegi, A.; Gabilondo, N.; Corcuera, M. A.; Eceiza, A. Synthesis and Characterization of Polyurethanes with High Renewable Carbon Content and Tailored Properties. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2016**, *4*, 5684–5692.
- (32) Calvo-Correas, T.; Santamaria-Echart, A.; Saralegi, A.; Martin, L.; Valea, Á.; Corcuera, M. A.; Eceiza, A. Thermally-Responsive Biopolyurethanes from a Biobased Diisocyanate. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2015**, *70*, 173–185.
- (33) Rousseau, I. A. Changes of Shape Memory Polymers: A Review of the Progress toward Overcoming SMP's Limitations. *Polym. Eng. Sci.* **2008**, *48*, 2075–2089.

- (34) Shirole, A.; Nicharat, A.; Perotto, C. U.; Weder, C. Tailoring the Properties of a Shape-Memory Polyurethane via Nanocomposite Formation and Nucleation. *Macromolecules* **2018**, *51*, 1841–1849.
- (35) Nicharat, A.; Shirole, A.; Foster, E. J.; Weder, C. Thermally Activated Shape Memory Behavior of Melt-Mixed Polyurethane/Cellulose Nanocrystal Composites. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2017**, *134*, 1–10.
- (36) Sonseca, Á.; Camarero-Espinosa, S.; Peponi, L.; Weder, C.; Foster, E. J.; Kenny, J. M.; Giménez, E. Mechanical and Shape-Memory Properties of Poly(Mannitol Sebacate)/Cellulose Nanocrystal Nanocomposites. *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.* **2014**, *52*, 3123–3133.
- (37) Fonseca, M. A.; Abreu, B.; Gonçalves, F. A. M. M.; Ferreira, A. G. M.; Moreira, R. A. S.; Oliveira, M. S. A. Shape Memory Polyurethanes Reinforced with Carbon Nanotubes. *Compos. Struct.* **2013**, *99*, 105–111.
- (38) Saralegi, A.; Fernandes, S. C. M.; Alonso-Varona, A.; Palomares, T.; Foster, E. J.; Weder, C.; Eceiza, A.; Corcuera, M. A. Shape-Memory Bionanocomposites Based on Chitin Nanocrystals and Thermoplastic Polyurethane with a Highly Crystalline Soft Segment. *Biomacromolecules* **2013**, *14*, 4475–4482.
- (39) Xu, B.; Huang, W. M.; Pei, Y. T.; Chen, Z. G.; Kraft, A.; Reuben, R.; De Hosson, J. T. M.; Fu, Y. Q. Mechanical Properties of Attapulgite Clay Reinforced Polyurethane Shape-Memory Nanocomposites. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2009**, *45*, 1904–1911.
- (40) Kim, J. T.; Kim, B. K.; Kim, E. Y.; Park, H. C.; Jeong, H. M. Synthesis and Shape Memory Performance of Polyurethane/Graphene Nanocomposites. *React. Funct. Polym.* **2014**, *74*, 16–21.
- (41) Hu, J. L.; Ji, F. L.; Wong, Y. W. Dependency of the Shape Memory Properties of a Polyurethane upon Thermomechanical Cyclic Conditions. *Polym. Int.* **2005**, *54*, 600–605.
- (42) Sun, J.; Zhou, S.; Hou, P.; Yang, Y.; Weng, J.; Li, X.; Li, M. Synthesis and Characterization of Biocompatible Fe₃O₄. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. Part A* **2007**, *80*, 333–341.
- (43) Saralegi, A.; Rueda, L.; Fernández-d'Arlas, B.; Mondragon, I.; Eceiza, A.; Corcuera, M. A. Thermoplastic Polyurethanes from Renewable Resources: Effect

of Soft Segment Chemical Structure and Molecular Weight on Morphology and Final Properties. *Polym. Int.* **2013**, *62*, 106–115.

- (44) Rueda, L.; Saralegi, A.; Fernández-d'Arlas, B.; Zhou, Q.; Alonso-Varona, A.; Berglund, L. A.; Mondragon, I.; Corcuera, M. A.; Eceiza, A. In Situ Polymerization and Characterization of Elastomeric Polyurethane-Cellulose Nanocrystal Nanocomposites. Cell Response Evaluation. *Cellulose* **2013**, *20*, 1819–1828.
- (45) International Organization for Standardization. ISO 10993-12:2009. Biological Evaluation of Medical Devices. Part 12: Sample Preparation and Reference Materials. 2009, pp 1–17.
- (46) International Organization for Standardization. ISO 10993-5. Biological Evaluation of Medical Devices. Test for in Vitro Cytotoxicity. Geneve, Switzerland 2009, pp 1–34.
- (47) International Organization for Standardization. ISO 10993-4:2009. Biological Evaluation of Medical Devices. Part 4: Selection of Tests for Interactions with Blood. Geneve, Switzerland 2009, pp 1–34.
- (48) Chowdhury, S. M.; Kanakia, S.; Toussaint, J. D.; Frame, M. D.; Dewar, A. M.; Shroyer, K. R.; Moore, W.; Sitharaman, B. In Vitro Hematological and in Vivo Vasoactivity Assessment of Dextran Functionalized Graphene. *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3*, 2584.
- (49) Rueda-Larraz, L.; Fernández-d'Arlas, B.; Tercjak, A.; Ribes, A.; Mondragon, I.; Eceiza, A. Synthesis and Microstructure-Mechanical Property Relationships of Segmented Polyurethanes Based on a PCL-PTHF-PCL Block Copolymer as Soft Segment. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2009**, *45*, 2096–2109.
- (50) Calvo-Correas, T.; Garrido, P.; Alonso-Varona, A.; Palomares, T.; Corcuera, M. A.; Eceiza, A. Biocompatible Thermoresponsive Polyurethane Bionanocomposites with Chitin Nanocrystals. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2019**, *136*, 1–12.
- (51) Kim, B. K.; Lee, S. Y.; Xu, M. Polyurethanes Having Shape Memory Effects. *Polymer* **1996**, *37*, 5781–5793.
- (52) Ratna, D.; Karger-Kocsis, J. Recent Advances in Shape Memory Polymers and Composites: A Review. *J. Mater. Sci.* **2008**, *43*, 254–269.

- (53) Cao, X.; Dong, H.; Li, C. M. New Nanocomposite Materials Reinforced with Flax Cellulose Nanocrystals in Waterborne Polyurethane. *Biomacromolecules* **2007**, *8*, 889–904.
- (54) Santamaria-Echart, A.; Ugarte, L.; García-Astrain, C.; Arbelaiz, A.; Corcuera, M. A.; Eceiza, A. Cellulose Nanocrystals Reinforced Environmentally-Friendly Waterborne Polyurethane Nanocomposites. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2016**, *151*, 1203–1209.
- (55) Kong, X.; Zhao, L.; Curtis, J. M. Polyurethane Nanocomposites Incorporating Biobased Polyols and Reinforced with a Low Fraction of Cellulose Nanocrystals. *Carbohydr. Polym.* **2016**, *152*, 487–495.
- (56) Lin, N.; Wei, S.; Xia, T.; Hu, F.; Huang, J.; Dufresne, A. Green Bionanocomposites from High-Elasticity “Soft” Polyurethane and High-Crystallinity “Rigid” Chitin Nanocrystals with Controlled Surface Acetylation. *RSC Adv.* **2014**, *4*, 49098–49107.
- (57) Guo, W.; Kang, H.; Chen, Y.; Guo, B.; Zhang, L. Stronger and Faster Degradable Biobased Poly(Propylene Sebacate) as Shape Memory Polymer by Incorporating Boehmite Nanoplatelets. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2012**, *4*, 4006–4014.
- (58) Xie, T. Recent Advances in Polymer Shape Memory. *Polymer* **2011**, *52*, 4985–5000.
- (59) Fernández-d’Arlas, B.; Ramos, J. A.; Saralegi, A.; Corcuera, M.; Mondragon, I.; Eceiza, A. Molecular Engineering of Elastic and Strong Supertough Polyurethanes. *Macromolecules* **2012**, *45*, 3436–3443.

IMPACT OF THE COMBINED USE OF MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES AND CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS ON THE SHAPE-MEMORY BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID POLYURETHANE BIONANOCOMPOSITES

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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Figure S1. a) XRD patterns of the CNCs. b) AFM height image ($5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$) of CNCs and c) height profile related to the red line in the height AFM image.

The XRD pattern shows a strong peak at $2\theta = 22.9^\circ$ and three minor peaks at $2\theta = 15.2$, 16.6 and 34.8° , corresponding to the (002), (101), $(10\bar{1})$ and (040) crystallographic planes of the cellulose I crystal structure. The crystallinity of the isolated CNCs was equal to 85%, as determined from the diffractogram using the method reported by Segal et al.,¹ which allows determining the crystallinity index from the ratio of the height of the (002) peak and the intensity scattered by the amorphous part of the CNC, located at 18° (I_{am}).

$$\text{CrI} = \frac{I_{002} - I_{\text{am}}}{I_{002}} \cdot 100$$

[1] Segal, L.; Creely, J. J.; Martin, A. E. J.; Conrad, C. M. An Empirical Method for Estimating the Degree of Crystallinity of Native Cellulose Using the X-Ray Diffractometer. *Text. Res. J.* **1958**, *29*, 786–794.

Figure S2. XRD patterns of the macrodiol, PU, PU-CNC and PU-3MNP-CNC. The inset shows a magnification of the range between 21 and 25°.

All prepared materials show two strong peaks which can be observed in the macrodiol (although they are slightly shifted) and thus must be related to the crystallizable macrodiol-rich domains. The peak observed in the macrodiol at $2\theta = 24.7^\circ$ appears at smaller angle, $2\theta = 24.4^\circ$, in the prepared PU and bionanocomposites, denoting different crystallization behavior when incorporated in the PU. Furthermore, in nanocomposites in which both nanofillers were combined, the intensity of the peak at $2\theta = 21.4^\circ$ decreases if compared to the neat PU, denoting a lower crystallinity, agreeing with the DSC results discussed in the manuscripts. Moreover, the observed peak at $2\theta = 22.9^\circ$ in the prepared bionanocomposites, confirms the presence of CNCs in both materials, since this peak is also observed in the XRD pattern of neat CNCs (Figure S1a).